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TUNABLE SELF-SENSING PERFORMANCE OF ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING-ENABLED PLA NANOCOMPOSITES FOR BIOMEDICAL APPLICATIONS

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Introduction

Bio-degradable scaffolds for tissue regeneration

- Supporting structures for repairing of damaged tissue or organs
- Act as carriers for growing bone tissue, cartilage, ligaments, skins, blood vessels, nerves and muscles
- Bio-degradability, Bio-compatibility, mechanical properties, porosity, pore size and shape, surface area, interconnectivity of pores, toxicity and bio-activity are the important factors
- Commonly used materials are synthetic polymers, natural polymers and ceramics

Introduction

Cellular structures for scaffolds

- Usually, porosity reduces mechanical properties
- Scaffold structures should have sufficient mechanical properties and be mechanically stable during cell growth
- Nature-inspired synthetic micro- and nano-architected materials offer enhanced material properties such as low density, superior mechanical properties and high surface area
- Properties of cellular materials can be altered to suit the application by independently changing the architectural parameters such as unit cell configuration and symmetry, ligament size and shape, nodal topology and the constituent material

Octet-truss

Kelvin foam

Introduction

Self-sensing scaffolds

- Scaffolds degrade and the new tissues grow
- Presently, no easy method exists that could assess the degradation of scaffold in use.
- Scaffold structures with self-sensing capability could enable easy monitoring of degree of degradation in vivo
- Self sensing capability could also help to assess the extent of tissue growth
- Piezo-resistive response of PLA/CNT composite can be utilized to develop self-sensing scaffold structures

Filament fabrication and 3D printing

- PLA/CNT composite filament for 3D printing is made by melt extrusion process using co-rotating twin-screw extruder
- Flashforge Creator 3 dual extruder 3D printer (Fused deposition modelling technique) is used for PLA/CNT composite specimen fabrication
- Bulk samples for tension and compression tests and cellular structures for compression tests (FCC plate lattice, kelvin foam and gyroid structures) are 3D printed

Filament fabrication and 3D printing

Additively manufactured cellular structures

Results and discussion

Mechanical response under tensile loading

Results and discussion

Mechanical and piezoresistive response under tensile loading

	Young's modulus (MPa)	Yield stress (MPa)	Gauge factor
PLA / 0°	1375	55	NA
PLA / 90°	1240	46	NA
PLA + 3 wt% CNT / 0°	1803 (+31%)	72 (+31%)	3.2
PLA + 3 wt% CNT / 90°	1736 (+40%)	60 (+30%)	1.4

Results and discussion

Mechanical and piezoresistive response under compressive loading

	Young's modulus (MPa)	Gauge factor
PLA	1336	NA
PLA + 3 wt% CNT	1764 (+32%)	2.47

Results and discussion

Mechanical response of cellular structures

Relative density = 20%

Results and discussion

Mechanical and piezoresistive response of cellular structures

	Modulus (MPa)	Gauge factor
FCC - PLA	125	NA
Kelvin - PLA	83	NA
Gyroid - PLA	173	NA
FCC - PLA + 3 wt% CNT	150 (+20%)	12.78
Kelvin - PLA + 3 wt% CNT	97 (+17%)	11
Gyroid - PLA + 3 wt% CNT	219 (+27%)	12.9

Conclusions

- Nanoengineered PLA/CNT composite filaments were developed by melt blending for FFF 3D printing
- Mechanical tests on 3D printed bulk composite samples show improved mechanical performance (modulus increase of >30% and yield stress increase of ~30%) and self-sensing property (Gauge factor ranging from 1.4 to 3.2)
- Cellular structures were fabricated via 3D printing and their mechanical and piezoresistive behavior was evaluated. Cellular structures show higher gauge factor (ranging from 11 to 12.9) compared to bulk samples.
- Higher sensitivity of PLA/CNT cellular architectures suggest their utility for self-sensing structures. This study could lead to a new route for manufacturing biodegradable scaffolds with self-sensing property.
- Scaffolds with self-sensing property could be beneficial in assessing the degree of degradation of implanted scaffolds and the extent of tissue growth in-vivo
- Mechanical and piezoresistive behavior of PLA/CNT composites with varying CNT content need to be analyzed.
- Bio-activity properties of PLA/CNT bulk samples and scaffolds need to be evaluated.

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